

DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of the child's personality, the factors influencing the development of the child, the importance of activities (play, exercise, work) in the development of the child, as well as the age stages of the child's mental development and about their peculiarities.

Keywords: Individual Personality, Developmental Environment, Activity, Biogenetics, Age Stages, Early Childhood, Early Childhood to Preschool.

РАЗВИТИЕ И ВОСПИТАНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается развитие личности ребенка, факторы, влияющие на развитие ребенка, важность видов деятельности (игры, физические упражнения, работа) в развитии ребенка, а также возрастные этапы психического развития ребенка и их особенности.

Ключевые слова: Индивидуальная личность, Развивающая среда, Деятельность, Биогенетика, Возрастные этапы, Раннее детство, Переход от раннего детства к дошкольному.

A newborn baby is considered an individual for a certain period of time. Derived from the individual Latin word, it means "indivisible", "separate shahe", "single". An individual is a separate living being belonging to a biological species. Movement is unique in the development of the child. The first-year child also forms a variety of movements, which are then conditioned reflexes, not consciously but occurs in response to unconditional and conditioned stimuli. The formation of speech in an early age child and the fact that the actions organized by the child begin to occur consciously and his participation in the process of social relations is the first stage of development of the child as a person.

Hence, development is a physical, mental, and social process in a person that involves all the properly acquired quantitative and qualitative changes. Physical development is associated with height and weight, increased muscle strength, perfection of sensory organs, ability to control movements correctly, and the like. In mental development, on the other hand, there are significant changes in the process of formation of mental qualities and traits in the personality, emotional (volitional), being. When a child begins to participate in social life, it is reflected in his behavior, his attitude towards the environment, and especially his participation in community work. Biological and social factors play a leading role in the development of the child, that is, in the formation of personality, in the occurrence of such physical and mental changes in the child.

"Person" means a member of a particular society. In order to be a shahe, one must be distinguished from others by his character and qualities that are spiritually developed. Everyone manifests differently as a shahe. He differs from others in his character, interests, abilities, level of mental development, needs, and personal attitude toward work activities. These are the characteristics of a person, and only when these qualities develop to a certain stage, he

will appear as a mature person. Hence, the social being of man is important to him in the conditions of socio-economic life (environment). The improvement of the environment and upbringing ensures that a person develops and manifests himself as a person. The formation of the child shaheen is associated with a number of factors, which are reflected in the following figure.

Research in the sciences of physiology and psychology has shown that the human child is born not with a ready ability, but with a capacity that is the source for the realization and development of a certain ability. The ability is in a state of "sleep" and requires a favorable environment and environment for its awakening and development. Man is a product of a particular social order. With this system change, the living environment in which the activity of change also takes place in a person can have a positive or negative effect on him. An environment is a set of external worlds that affect the formation of a child's personality. The formation of the individual is carried out through the assimilation and upbringing of the socio-historical experience created by human society. As a result of education, the child begins to interact or interact with the social system in the society in which he lives. Upbringing varies depending on the child's "pre-developmental zone", ie it is determined by the child's ability to acquire more complex, meaningful knowledge. For example, the transition to walking after the baby has mastered crawling, the transition to active speech after learning to say certain joints, the emergence of play, labor activity, etc. after learning to move with objects. Education plays a leading role in the formation of the child's personality, in the implementation of this work. This increases their responsibility in the formation of each child's personality.

Education is affected in relation to all of the educational influences that come through the social environment. It uses convenient effective factors, which to some extent reduces the strength of adverse effects. The following situations occur in the educational process. In the process of education, the human body develops, and things that cannot spontaneously provide the environment are learned through education. For example, a child may learn his or her mother tongue under the influence of the environment around him or her. But he learns to read and write through special education. Certain knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired in the educational process. With the help of education, some of the child's birth defects can be changed in the desired direction. For example, some children are born with certain defects. (deaf, dumb, blind, etc.). With the help of education, it is possible to eliminate some of the shortcomings that have occurred as a result of the negative impact of the environment. Different types of activities are formed on the basis of activity in the educational process. Their main ones are communication activities, cognition, object activities, play, simple labor and learning activities, and activities that are carried out through education and upbringing. They are gradually mastered by children under the guidance of a tutor. The successful acquisition of various activities by children depends mainly on the organization of educational work in kindergarten depends on. The most common type of activity in a person's life is the basis for the formation of a certain relationship based on his personal abilities and characteristics. Activity develops by mastering the ways of movement. The extent to which it develops from activism depends more on heredity and the ability to imitate. One of the main tasks is to educate and train the child from an early age in the family and in preschool institutions through the child's interaction with objects and things.

In the growth activities that are important for the preschool period, children learn about things and objects under the guidance of an educator and learn about their qualities and characteristics. Through movement games performed together, children learn about people's lives, the relationships between them, and how to act in harmony. In this way, children's perceptions of the environment expand. Hence, activity plays a leading role in the upbringing and development of the child. Therefore, it is important to organize the life of the child in educational institutions and in the family in such a way that he can engage in various activities. There are preschool age, school age period as well as social maturity and adulthood in human life. Within each of these periods are shorter stages of age, which are distinguished by certain peculiarities in human development. For example, the task, content, means and methods of educational work with children of the first age are developed taking into account the sensitivity of children of this age, their need for help, their adaptability to life. By the age of another, children will have significantly increased resilience to independence and life. Accordingly, the methods of carrying out educational work with children of this age will change. By the end of kindergarten, the level of development of children requires a certain complication of the educational work carried out with them.

The task of determining the content and method of educational work is based on the age of the person. Early childhood children are characterized by their rapid movement, helplessness, rapid onset of illness, need for help. Speech development in children under the age of three is one of the hallmarks of this period. Three-year-olds master all aspects of their mother tongue and use it as a tool in communication with their peers. The system of early childhood education is an integral part of the upbringing of the younger generation. Physiologists, psychologists, educators contribute to the social upbringing of children around the world. By the age of kindergarten, the child's body continues to mature. Kindergarten children begin to understand the nature of the demands placed on them.

In addition to adult reprimands for misbehavior and misconduct, he also tries to draw independent and correct conclusions. Hence, the task of upbringing is to identify the talents and abilities in the child in a timely manner and help them to develop further. In the process of education, it is possible to achieve the goals of education, taking into account the specific characteristics of each child.

REFERENCES

1. Мўйдинов, А. (2021). ЁШЛАРНИ ТУРЛИ ТАҲДИДЛАРДАН ҲИМОЯ ҚИЛИШДА АЖДОДЛАР МЕРОСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 132-137.
2. Asilbek, M. (2022). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION OF AN ENLIGHTENED PERSON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Conferencea*, 183-186.
3. Adham o'g'li, M. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL WITCHCRAFT HERITAGE IN THE SPIRITUAL RISE OF SOCIETY (SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS). *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 122-127.
4. Muydinov, A. (2022). ENLIGHTENMENT IN TURKESTAN IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX-EARLY XX CENTURIES. ENLIGHTENMENT BY JADID SCHOOL. *ASIA*

- PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836
Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 14-20.
5. Ruzmatovich, U. S. (2022). PROCESSES OF ORGANIZATION OF TECHNICAL, TACTICAL AND PHYSICAL PREPARATION IN NATIONAL WRESTLING TRAINING. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 65-68.
 6. Ruzmatovich, U. S. (2022). CHANGES EXPECTED TO COME IN OUR LIFE MOVEMENTS. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(3), 485-489.
 7. Shohbozjon, K., & Azizjon, M. (2022). PREPARING SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS BEFORE ENTRY TO HIGHER EDUCATION. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(10), 100-108.
 8. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Developing Critical Thinking In Primary School Students. Conferencea, 97-102.
 9. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8(2), 235-239.
 10. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal, 11(2), 326-329.
 11. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). Methodical Support Of Development Of Creative Activity Of Primary School Students. Conferencea, 74-76.
 12. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 203-207.
 13. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 2, 121-123.
 14. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 289-292.
 15. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 235-239.
 16. Махамдалиевна, Y. D., Òljayevna, Ò. F., Qizi, T. D. T., Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Anvarovna, A. O. (2020). Pedagogical Features Of Mental Development Of Preschool Children. Solid State Technology, 63(6), 14221-14225.
 17. Sharofutdinova, R. I., Asadullaev, A. N., & Tolibova, Z. X. (2021). The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 2(5), 376-379.
 18. Iqboljon, S. (2022). Boshlang'ich Sinf o'quv Jarayonida Axborot Texnologiyalaridan Foydalanish. Ijodkor o'qituvchi, 2(20), 137-140.

19. Iqboljon, S. (2022). KOMPYUTER YORDAMIDA DARSLARNI TASHKIL ETISH. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 1(9), 246-249.
20. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 424-429.
21. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). THE ACTUAL STATUS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(12), 206-213.
22. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINING AMALIYOTDA QOLLASH. *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(7), 54-58.
23. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK FANLARNING BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI O 'RNI. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(6), 17-24.
24. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA'LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK TIZIMI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 2(14), 13-19.
25. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA'LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(13), 77-84.
26. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION INFORMATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(4), 574-580.
27. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). FORMS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON THE ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF INFORMATIZATION OF EDUCATION. *Science and innovation*, 2(B3), 5-8.
28. Usmonjon o'g'li, S. I. (2022). TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNALOGIYA. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 120-128.
29. Абдужабборов, А., & Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИДА ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ҚАРАТИЛГАН ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ.
30. Sharofutdinova, R., & Abduqodirov, B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 904-910.
31. Sharafutdinova, R., & Abdujabborov, A. (2023). EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 890-896.

32. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). ИЖОД ТУШУНЧАСИ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМИ. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(19), 854-861.
33. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ-ИЖТИМОЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТ СИФАТИДА. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(19), 842-847.
34. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдукодилов, Б. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ ВА ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(19), 862-868.
35. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдужабборов, А. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАНЛИГИДА ҲАМКОРЛИК КЛАСТЕРИ. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(19), 848-853.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Sohibaxon, S. (2023). MAXSUS TA'LIMNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(19), 830-836.
37. Ra'noxon, S., Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(11), 881-885.
38. Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(11), 213-217.
39. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., & O'ljayevna, O. R. F. (2020). Tursunova Dilnavoz To 'lqin qizi, Sharofutdinova Ra'noxon Shavkatovna, Ashurova Oygul Anvarovna. Pedagogical features of mental development of preschool children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6).
40. Mirzaxolmatovna, X. Z., Nematovna, R. S., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2022). FORMS OF THINKING IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING MATHEMATICS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 259-263.
41. Ganiev, A. A., Abdullaev, S. Y., & Abdurahmonov, S. Z. (2021). Combined treatment for early-stage skin cancer of the head and neck area. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 4, 3-6.
42. Ganiev, A. A., & kizi Ganieva, O. O. TASAVVUF TARIQATI YO 'NALISHLARI VA NAQSHBANDIYA TARIQATINING O 'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.
43. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Uzbekistan's General Education School Physical Education Programme: A Curriculum Analysis. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 184-193.
44. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Examining the First Age Group's Health Test Needs for "Salomatlik" Regulation Using the Dynamic of Children's

- Motor Potential. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(5), 194-200.
45. Kosimov, K., & Mamayusupov, J. (2019). Transitions melline integral of fractional integrodifferential operators. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(1), 12-15.
46. Qo'Ziyev, S. S., & Mamayusupov, J. S. (2021). Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari uchun elektron darslik yaratishning pedagogik shartlari. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 447-453.
47. Мамаюсупов, Ж. Ш. (2022). Интегральное преобразование Меллина для оператора интегродифференцирования дробного порядка. Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities, 11, 186-188.
48. Mamayusupov, J. S. O. (2022). "IQTISOD" YO'NALISHI MUTAXASSISLARINI TAYYORLASHDA MATEMATIKA FANINI O'QITISH USLUBIYOTI. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(3), 720-728.
49. Mamayusupov, J., & Sattarov, A. (2022). Mellin Integral Replacement and its Applications. Eurasian Research Bulletin, 15, 256-263.
50. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). PISA XALQARO BAHOLASH TIZIMI VA UNING MATEMATIK AHAMIYATI. Journal of new century innovations, 25(1), 3-8.
51. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). MATEMATIK MODEL VA MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING UMUMIY PRINSIPLARI. World scientific research journal, 13(1), 45-48.
52. Vasiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 3(2), 1-3.
53. Vasiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 176-182.
54. Vasiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILIIY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 99-105.
55. Vasiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGUISTICS AND THE HISTORY OF ITS ANALYTICAL DEVELOPMENT. Science and Innovation, 1(8), 99-105.
56. Vasiljonov, A., & Isaqova, X. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(2).
57. KHALIMBOYEVA, F., & VOSILJONOV, A. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR DIQQATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOSINI NAZARIY O'RGANILISHI. Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies, 1(5), 94-98.
58. Soxibov, S. (2023). THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IS A HUGE TASK. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 1037-1041.
59. Soxibov, S. (2023). MEASURES TO FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 1031-1036.
60. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL-ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND PREVENTION OF CORRUPT RELATIONS. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(3).

61. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2021, April). THE ROLE OF RELIGIOUS AND MORAL EDUCATION IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION, ALONG WITH THE USE OF ECONOMIC AND LEGAL FACTORS. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 55-57).
62. Нажмиддинов, Э., & Мухамедиев, М. (2023). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
63. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., & Мухаммадиев, М. А. (2022). ФАРҒОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИНИНГ ТУР ТАРКИБИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 60-68.
64. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х. (2022). ФАРҒОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИ. *ЎТМОЎЙ ФАНЛАРДА ИННОВАСИЯ ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ*, 2(11), 189-194.
65. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NATURE IN THE FORMATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE IDEAL GENERATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 149-154.
66. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). " ICHTHYOLOGY AND HYDROBIOLOGY" PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 152-160.
67. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE NEED TO IMPROVE HUMAN'S NOOSPHERICAL RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 23-30.
68. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING PERSONAL ECOLOGICAL CULTURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 5-12.
69. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). АТРОФ-МУҲИТНИ АСРАШ БЎЙИЧА МИЛЛИЙ СТРАТЕГИК РЕЖА ВА УНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 251-258.
70. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). ЯНГИ ТАРАҚҚИЁТ БОСҚИЧИДА ЭКОЛОГИК МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ДАСТУРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 1179-1186.
71. Абдумаликов, А. А. (2019). Human and Natural Harmony in the Historical Process. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 205-209.
72. Abidzhanovich, A. A. (2020). Issues Of Formation Of Rationality In Relations Of Nature With Society. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 301-304.
73. Abdumalikov, A. A. (2019). Environmental Ecological Policy in Uzbekistan and Necessity Of Formation Of Rational Communication To Nature. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(9), 94-101.
74. Мирзабоев, Й. А. (2022). Тур Ўзгариш Чизиқлари Учта Бўлган, Гиперболик Қисмларининг Ҳаммаси Харақтеристик Учбурчаклардан Иборат Бўлган Бешбурчакли Соҳада Учтинчи Тартибли Кўринишдаги Параболик-Гиперболик Тенглама Учун Битта Чегаравий Масала Ҳақида. *Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research*, 1(5), 363-366.

75. MIRZABOYEV, Y. BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QITUVCHILARINING MATEMATIKA O'QITISH METODIKASI. O'RTA UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA MATEMATIKA O'QITISHNING MAQSADI. ЭКОНОМИКА, 169-172.
76. Iminov, B. B. (2020). INNOVATIVE CULTURAL LINKS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(3), 263-270.
77. Iminov, B. B. (2019). A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO INNOVATIVE AND CULTURAL-RELATIONS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(5), 157-162.
78. Qizi, S. G. G. O. (2022). LINGUISTIC BASIS AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF TEACHING WORD MEANING TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(12), 117-123.
79. Qizi, S. G. G., & Teshaboyevna, D. D. Methods Of Formation Of Independent Reading Skills In Primary School Pupils. JournalNX, 21-24.
80. Kizi, S. G. G. (2021). Formation Of Independent Reading Skills in Primary School Students. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 2, 222-224.
81. Valijonovna, K. I., Rakhmatjonovich, T. D., & Mukhtoralievna, Z. S. (2022). Informational Technology at Education. Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity, 6, 262-266.
82. Akmaljonovna, A. Z. (2021). Methods of formation of independent reading skills in primary school students. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1425-1428.
83. Dehqonova, M., & Tagonova, G. (2022). The Importance of Didactic Games in Speech Therapy in the Development of Speech in Children with Autism and the Ability to Choose Effective Methods. European Journal of Innovation In Nonformal Education, 2(1), 133-137.
84. Dehqonova, M. (2022). BOLALARDAGI YOZUV BUZILISHLARI VA ULARDAGI DISGRAFIYADA O'ZIGA XOS XATOLIKLARNI PAYDO BO'LIQ MEXANIZMI. YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR, 405-407.
85. Dehqonova, M., & Najmiddinova, N. (2022). ALOHIDA EHTIYOJGA EGA BO'LGAN BOLALARNING OILAGA MOSLASHISHI UCHUN MUHIM OMILLAR. YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR, 90-92.
86. Dehqonova, M. (2023). MAXSUS MAKTABDA DAKTIL NUTQINI O'QITISH-TADQIQOT OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. Наука и инновация, 1(1), 39-40.
87. Qizi, D. M. S., & Qizi, R. G. X. (2022). METHODS OF STUDYING ADDITION AND SUBTRACTION OF TWO-DIGIT NUMBERS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 22, 61-67.
88. Dehqonova, M. S. Q., & Axmedova, U. Y. Q. (2023). BO'LAJAK BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QITUVCHILARINI MATEMATIK SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH JARAYONIDA ULARNING TAFAKKURI, QOBILIYATI VA INTELLEKTUAL RIVOJLANISH. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(4-2), 251-256.
89. Otazhonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Botirov, K. A., Qaxxorova, B. A., Xudoynazarova, M. A., Abdulkarimova, N. A., ... & Ismoilova, E. M. (2022, December). Influence of thickness and temperature on photoelectric properties of p-CdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-CdSe heterostructures. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012001). IOP Publishing.

90. Otajonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Axmedov, T., Usmonov, Y., & Karimov, B. (2022, December). Photoelectric properties of solar cells based on pCdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-nCdSe heterostructures. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012062). IOP Publishing.
91. Abdulvakhidov, K., Li, Z., Abdulvakhidov, B., Soldatov, A., Otajonov, S., Ergashev, R., ... & Sitalo, E. (2023). Structure phase state and physical properties of $\text{YbMn}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_x\text{O}_3$ compositions. *Applied Physics A*, 129(3), 185.
92. Ahmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2021). *Vatanim Surati. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 877-883.
93. Axmedova, U. (2022). On Certain Conditions Of Striking Coefficients Of Fourier Series To Zero. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 3-8.
94. Qizi, A. U. Y., & Qizi, A. M. U. B. (2021). Research On Hydronyms and Their Importance.
95. Umidaxon, A., & Gulirano, S. (2023). Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida amaliy mashqlar yechish jarayonida o'quvchilarning fikrlash qobiliyatini ostirish omillari. *Pedagogika, psixologiya va ijtimoiy tadqiqotlar*, 2(5), 10-14.
96. Axmedov, O. U. B. O. G., & Qizi, A. U. Y. (2022). STEREOMETRIYA BO'LIMI VA UNING BA'ZI AKSIOMALARIDAN KELIB CHIQUADIGAN NATIJALAR. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 127-133.
97. Axmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2022). XALQ OG 'ZAKI IJOD NAMUNALARINING BOSHLANG 'ICH SINFLIKLARIDA QO 'LLANISHI VA ULARNING MAZMUNY GURUHLANISHI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 345-351.
98. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). Educational Methods in Teaching the Russian Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 260-263.
99. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 138-145.
100. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING INNOVATIVE METHODS. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 132-135.
101. Erkinovna, N. S. (2023). RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN WORLD. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 284-295.
102. Rakhmatjonov Shokhjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //the role of physical culture in providing the psychological health of the athlete// innovative developments and research in education. *International scientific online conference. Canada. Part 2, 23.01.2022.* 1-3
103. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //SPORTCHI PSIXOLOGIK SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR// *GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ)*. Vol. 10, Issue 11, Nov.(2022). 117-121 pages.
104. QURBONOVA Saida Miralimjanovna, RAXMATJONOV Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //MAMLAKATIMIZ PSIXOLOGLARI ISHLARIDA SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATDA MUOMALA MUAMMOSINING TALQINI// *Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies*. Vol. 1. № 5, (2023). 99-103 pages.

105. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li // SPEECH ISSUES IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS// IQRO JURNALI № 2. 04.2023. 503-511 betlar.
106. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li, Vosiljonov Azizbek Boxodirjon o'g'li // XORIY PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI// INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. Vol. 1. № 12, 2022. 39-47 pages.
107. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li // TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH – IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA// International Journal of Economy and Innovation. Volume: 30. 2022. 66-70 pages.
108. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li // PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS// IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. Vol. 2 No. 11 (2022). 215-221 betlar.
109. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li // Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi// American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, Vol. 3 No. 11 (2022). 256-259 pages.
110. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li // TOLERANTLIK SHAKLLANAYOTGAN SHAXS MODELINING TAVSIFI// International scientific journal «MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH». VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 5 / 2023. 761-764 pages.
111. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYADA MOTIVATSIYA TURLARI, NAZARIYALARI VA TAHLILI. Научный Импульс, 1(10), 665-670.
112. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF WAYS TO BUILD A SELF-SIMILAR SOLUTION. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 950-958.
113. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF PROCESSES WITH CONVECTIVE TRANSPORT. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 941-949.
114. Kadirov, S. (2023). Historical and cultural monuments and their condition in fergana region (1991-2020 in the case of the city of margilan): the issue of preservation, protection and their use. Modern Science And Research, 2(5), 818-830.
115. Abduraxmonov, a., & kadirov, s. (2022). Demografik jarayonlarning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy sohalarni rivojlanishi bilan bog'liqligi va dastlabki xususiy mulk masalalari. Ijtimoiy fanlarda innovasiya onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 2(11), 222-229.
116. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODS FOR GROWING SPEECH SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 1028-1030.
117. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE NOUN PHRASE CATEGORY: ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING IN STUDENTS. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 1025-1027.
118. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2023). Superstitions in Linguoculturology. DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY", 14(1).
119. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). O 'QUVCHILAR NUTQINI O 'STIRISH METODIKASI. IQRO JURNALI, 2(2), 637-645.
120. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING NUTQDAGI O'RNI. IQRO, 2(2), 522-529.
121. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2022). ORIGIN AND CONCEPT OF TABOO VOCABULARY. Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal, 3(10), 184-190.